

Australian Government

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Defence Science and Technology Group

Discrete damage modelling of compressively loaded structural supercapacitors

Alex Harman, Benjamin J. Mapleback, Vu Dao, Lachlan Bodsworth, Patrick Frezza and Andrew N. Rider

Platforms Division

Defence Science and Technology Group

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PUBLIC RELEASE

- Background
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- Discrete damage modelling using BSAM™
- Conclusions
- Further work

Background

Greenhalgh, E., et.al., Critical review of structural supercapacitors, CS&T, 2023.

- Structural SuperCapacitors (SSC) are being developed for integration into carbon-epoxy composite aircraft structures – Designed for minimal impact on structural integrity
- 26 ply IM7/977-3 laminates prepared with three 50 mm diameter “semi-structural” SC’s and PTFE inserts integrated through the thickness
- Test method based on ASTM D7137 used for compression after impact (100 x 150 mm)

Background - configurations

50mm diameter/ SSC

Configuration A: SSC

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
[(45/-45/0₂/90)₂(45/-45/0)]_s

50mm diameter/
0.25mm PTFE insert

Configuration B: 0.25 mm PTFE

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
[(45/-45/0₂/90)₂(45/-45/0)]_s

Experimental testing – Pre-test NDE

Pulse-echo UT

Through transmission UT

Configuration A: SSC

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
[(45/-45/0₂/90)₂(45/-45/0)]_s

Pulse-echo UT

Through transmission UT

Configuration B: 0.25 mm PTFE

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
[(45/-45/0₂/90)₂(45/-45/0)]_s

Experimental testing – Mechanical response

CV = 1.84%

Configuration A: SSC

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
 $[(45/-45/0_2/90)_2(45/-45/0)]_S$

CV = 2.64%

Configuration B: 0.25 mm PTFE

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
 $[(45/-45/0_2/90)_2(45/-45/0)]_S$

* Average strength and max CH for **configuration A**
SSC used for normalisation

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SSC used for normalisation

Experimental testing – Configuration A SSC DIC

Configuration A: SSC

Experimental testing – Configuration B 0.25 mm PTFE DIC

Configuration B: 0.25 mm PTFE

Experimental testing – Post-test examination

Configuration A: SSC

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
[(45/-45/0₂/90)₂(45/-45/0)]_s

Configuration B: 0.25 mm PTFE

Base laminate: 26 ply IM7/977-3
[(45/-45/0₂/90)₂(45/-45/0)]_s

- “Insert region” represented as “filled cavities” that entailed two circular 0° ply “cut-outs”
- Modelling considerations included

 - G-control adjusted to “slow down” energy release for MIC/delam near failure for numerical stability
 - CDM enabled to model progressive compression failure of 0° fibres
 - Geometric linear and non-linear formulations were tried

Discrete damage modelling using BSAM™

Front

Back

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Conclusions

- Composite laminates with embedded SSC and PTFE defects were tested under compression with high repeatability (CV 1.84–2.64%).
- SSC specimens were ~10% stronger than PTFE, indicating a structural contribution from the SSC materials.
- Ultrasonic testing showed better sound transmission through SSC regions, confirming improved integrity.
- Sub-critical damage initiated earlier in SSC (60% failure load) than PTFE (85%), involving delamination and local instability.
- Final failure mode included translaminar fracture in both configurations.
- Non-linear BSAM analysis aligned better with experiments than linear analysis but still overpredicted failure by >25%.

Further work

- Apply newer versions of analysis software to improve prediction accuracy.
- Conduct more in-depth post-test examinations using X-ray micro-computed tomography (XmCT).
- Perform synchrotron experiments to observe SSC failure modes in greater detail.
- Investigate the structural contribution of SSC materials through high-resolution imaging and in situ testing.
- Refine modelling techniques based on insights from experimental characterisation

